

“To Study the Challenges and Opportunities of India’s Increased Participation in The Global Economy.”

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ABSTRACT:

The world economy has evolved considerably since World War II. The emerging market countries, other developed countries and economies in transition account for over one half of global GDP measured in terms of Purchasing Power Parity (PPP), holds most of the world’s currency reserves, and represent a majority of the world’s population. India is becoming a key player in the global economy after being criticized by economists for low growth. India has finally grabbed a place in the world’s emerging markets. India performs better in exporting information and technology services, pharmaceuticals and petroleum products. India’s large population or we can say dispersion is well integrated with other countries. This helps India to develop new markets for exports and facilitate the transfer of technologies. India could perform better in some areas. To encourage economic growth India could increase focus on infrastructure, transport, developing skills, reconsidering barriers to trade and investments and energy provisions. India can effectively prepare for its new global leadership thereby using the potential of its massive and unique human resources. This research paper contains various opportunities and challenges facing India in the global economy. In this report I draw the balance sheet of India’s achievements and challenges, in the context of the emerging ranking in the global economy.

Keywords: Global Economy, Leadership, Resources, Balance Sheet

I.INTRODUCTION:

The participation of India in the global economy has risen and is high, in terms of GDP, trade, number of Indians living in other countries, although less so in terms of international capital. India has developed expertise and succeeded in exporting many goods and services to large number of countries. India has specialized in sectors will like to be in high demand in the near years. India's population the biggest in the world has helped develop the networks of trade while the remittances of migrants and also the savings have supported the domestic consumption and investment.

India the world's largest democracy has yet to recognize its full potential as a leading global economy. The rapid economic growth of India observed since the mid-90s was accompanied by various reforms. After being criticized by world's economists for low growth, India finally grabbed a place among the world's prominent emerging markets.

The economy of India is more integrated today and more reliant on the global economy than ever before. India has come a long way from decades of hindered economic growth, a brutally negative balance of payments, and exchange rate fluctuations and sporadic crises.

In the past, India opened up the economy in the early 90's following major catastrophe that led by a foreign exchange crisis that hauled the economy close to defaulting on loans. To face the challenges the government of India decided to bring the new policy to recover Economy of India. This policy was widely known as 'Structural Policy.' This New Economic Policy announced by government on July 24, 1991 and it is commonly known as LPG (Liberalization Privatization Globalization) policy. In this policy the Liberalization means the process of lifting the restrictions imposed by government like reduction of tariff or removal of non-tariff barriers etc. Privatization means the transfer of ownership of businesses or properties from government to private entities or firms and Globalization refers to the expanding the cultural, economic and political activities across the national boundaries. It is the movement and integration of goods and people among different countries.

II.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the opportunities which are seized by India in the global economy.
2. To understand the how India's trade contributes to economic growth.
3. To study the key challenges that India faces.
4. To find out the observations and suggestions in order to overcome the challenges.

III.REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Following the introduction of economic changes in India since 1991 scores of studies relating to its impact on Indian economy their challenges and opportunities in the global economy.

Singh (1964) long back had spoken extreme dissatisfaction towards the performance of external sector and import substitution policy followed by India. He recommended variety of changes in the export sector but regrettably its implementation come much later after the crisis in 1991.

According to Jalan (1991) the year 1990-1991 was the cruelest year in Indian History and the export performance since the independence was despondent when compared with other developing countries.

For Bhagawati and Srinivasan (1975) the industrialization policies followed by India in pre-reform period protected domestic industries from foreign competition but led to unnecessary or inappropriate state intervention in the market resulting high cost and low growth of Indian economy.

Patnaik and chandrashekhar (1995) they advised combination of three measures to control financial flows volatility in India namely direct regulations, sound balance of payments and a development strategy which guaranteed economic development.

Mathur (2005) expressed concern over the utilization of potential of International trade in India. As compared to East Asian countries, India's share in world market remained low.

Thus, various studies undertaken by the different researchers to assess the impact of economic changes, challenges in India. The study is significant in view of growing importance of India in the global economy.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The Research Methodology or Design adopted in the project is “Quantitative and Analytical Research”.

TYPE OF RESEARCH USED:

Quantitative Research is based on the measurement of quantity or amount. It applies to phenomena that can be expressed in terms of quantity.

In analytical research, the researcher has to use facts or information already available.

DATA COLLECTION

Data Collection is the process of gathering and measuring information. There are two types of data collection: i) Primary Data ii) Secondary Data. While analysing the topic data is collected from the secondary data.

SECONDARY DATA:

It consists of Reports & website of company, reference website, and books

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES USED

The data is being processed using various techniques & methods, use of diagram, tables chart. Then the some obtain from these facts & figures are compared with the past performance.

Presentation of Data:

The data collected is presented in the form of Tables, Bar diagrams – Doughnuts, Cylinder graphs, Line graphs. Graphs are shown to present the data wherever necessary. The tables are drawn to represent the data wherever necessary.

V. DATA ANALYSIS:

ACHIEVEMENTS OF INDIA

Fig 1. India has become the major actor in the global economy

Fig 1.A. GDP VOLUME (In Percentage)

COUNTRY	1996	2018
SOUTH AFRICA	0.43	0.4
INDONESIA	0.97	1.24
MEXICO	1.76	1.55
RUSSIAN FEDERATION	1.67	1.76
CANADA	2.29	2.05
ITALY	3.95	2.35
BRAZIL	2.60	2.23
INDIA	1.51	3.22
UNITED KINGDOM	4.55	3.77
FRANCE	4.23	3.17
GERMANY	6.13	4.43
JAPAN	9.01	5.62
CHINA	4.69	16.41
UNITED STATES	27.20	24.14

Fig 1.B. TRADE- GOODS & SERVICES (In Percentage of GDP)

COUNTRY	1996	2018
SOUTH AFRICA	0.12	0.12
INDONESIA	0.19	0.26
BRAZIL	0.22	0.32
RUSSIAN FEDERATION	0.29	0.48
MEXICO	0.34	0.59
INDIA	0.15	0.72
CANADA	0.65	0.67
ITALY	0.77	0.72
UNITED KINGDOM	0.92	1.08
FRANCE	0.79	1.01
JAPAN	0.99	1.05
GERMANY	1.24	2.00
CHINA	0.44	3.2
UNITED STATES	2.47	3.42

Fig 1.C. TOP 20 COUNTRIES WITH LARGEST POPULATION

COUNTRY	1995	2019
TURKEY	2.80	3.50
EGYPT	1.50	3.50
ROMANIA	1.00	3.60
MYANMAR	0.90	3.70
PALESTINIAN AUTHORITY	2.30	3.90
KAZAKHSTAN	3.30	4.00
GERMANY	3.00	4.00
UNITED KINGDOM	3.70	4.30
POLAND	1.80	4.40
INDOONESIA	2.00	4.50
AFGHANISTAN	3.70	5.10
PHILIPPINES	2.50	5.40
UKRAINE	5.60	5.90
PAKISTAN	3.30	6.30
BANGLADESH	5.40	7.80
SYRIAN REPUBLIC	0.70	8.20
ARAB		

RUSSIAN FEDERATION	11.60	10.50
CHINA	5.00	10.70
MEXICO	6.90	11.80
INDIA	7.20	17.50

Interpretation of Fig 1.(A, B & C):

The participation of India in the global economy has increased in terms of GDP, in 1996 the GDP of India was 1.51 and in 2018 it was 3.22. According to data India is the 7th largest economy (Fig.A). India has developed know how and succeeded in trading many goods and services according to data, in 1996 the trade of India was 0.15% and in 2018 it was 0.72 %. In mid-90's the trade of India has grown slowly but significantly (Fig.B). India's population is the largest in the world has helped develop trade connections while migrants remittances and savings which are generated from the population of India supported the domestic consumption and investment of the country (Fig.C).

Fig 2.Trade Intensity of India has increased

Fig 2.A. INDIA'S INTERNATIONAL TRADE(In Percentage of GDP)

YEAR S	EXPORT(Goods & Services)	IMPORT(Goods & Services)
1990	7.05	8.45
1991	8.49	8.49
1992	8.84	9.59
1993	9.83	9.82
1994	9.89	10.19
1995	10.84	12.02
1996	10.39	11.54
1997	10.69	11.93
1998	11.02	12.68
1999	11.45	13.36
2000	13.00	13.90
2001	12.56	13.43
2002	14.26	15.24
2003	14.95	15.64
2004	17.86	19.64
2005	19.61	22.40
2006	21.27	24.46
2007	20.80	24.89
2008	24.10	29.27
2009	20.40	25.87
2010	22.40	26.85
2011	24.54	31.08

2012	24.53	31.26
2013	25.43	28.41
2014	22.97	25.95
2015	19.81	22.11
2016	19.19	20.96
2017	18.78	21.99
2018	19.70	23.43

Fig 2.B. EXPORT 2018(In Percentage of GDP)

COUNTRY	GOODS	SERVICE
UNITED STATE	8.17	4.04
BRAZIL	12.77	1.82
JAPAN	14.80	3.90
CHINA	17.76	1.72

INDIA	12.18	7.52
INDONESIA	17.34	2.69
SOUTH AFRICA	25.54	4.33
GERMANY	38.21	8.58

Fig 2.C. IMPORT 2018(In Percentage of GDP)

COUNTRY	GOODS	SERVICE
BRAZIL	9.93	3.64
UNITED STATE	12.50	2.77
JAPAN	14.57	4.04
CHINA	14.86	3.86
INDONESIA	17.38	3.37
INDIA	19.03	4.55
SOUTH AFRICA	25.08	4.48
GERMANY	31.64	9.15

Interpretation of Fig 2.(A, B & C):

By the Figures we can see the trade intensity of India has increased expressively. From 2006 to 2014 the export increased rapidly as well as import increased comparatively more than the export. But after 2014 its decreased little bit but its not volatile. Compared to early years i.e.mid-90's it is much better and stable (Fig.A). The Government taking measures to increase the export of India and implementing different policies and for imports the government of India taking measures like applying import tariffs and non-tariff barriers.

Since, becoming more open to trade, India's Export and Imports to GDP ratio increased fast and now stand broadly at par with China (Fig.B& C). Indian exports also suffered from the appreciation of the rupee and from temporary disturbance in the domestic value chain associated with the 2016 demonetization and rise in the Goods and Service Tax (GST) in 2017.

Fig 3. India has specialized in faster growing markets.

Fig 3. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE 1996 AND 2017- VARIOUS MARKETS (In % of Gross Export Trade Flows)

	1996	2017
ICT	4.93	26.93
OTHER SERVICES	11.23	11.52
STONE & GLASS	11.82	9.52
CHEMICAL & PLASTIC	8.37	9.63
TEXTILE & FURNITURE	23.14	8.64

MINERALS	4.77	8.34
VEGETABLE, FOODSTUFF & WOOD	20.83	8.52
TRANSPORT VEHICLES	2.14	4.64
METALS	5.68	5.87
MACHINNERY	4.01	4.30
ELECTRONICS	1.95	1.86
OTHERS	1.13	0.23

Interpretation of Fig 3:

Export resilience partly reflects the gaining expertise of India in fast growing products especially the Service sector. India has become one of the major exporter of business services notably in the Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) Sector. In 1996 the ICT sector had 4.93% of gross export trade flows but in 2017 the total percentage of ICT sector export increased enormously 26.93%. But the export of textile and furniture lagged behind. It is decreased from 23.14% to 8.64%.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR INDIA TO GROW

Fig 4. The Large Population is an Asset.

Fig 4. A. TOP 10 COUNTRIES-POPULATIONS LIVING ABROAD (Millions)

COUNTRY	2019
AFGHANISTAN	5.10
PHILIPPINES	5.40
UKRAINE	5.90
PAKISTAN	6.30
BANGLADESH	7.80
SYRIA	8.20
RUSSIAN FEDERATION	10.50
CHINA	10.70
MEXICO	11.80
INDIA	17.50

Fig 4.B.REMITTANCES

COUNTRY	% OF GDP
CHILE	0.02
UNITED STATES	0.03
CANADA	0.08
JAPAN	0.09
ARGENTINA	0.10
TURKEY	0.15
BRAZIL	0.16
UNITED KINGDOM	0.16
CHINA	0.18
SOUTH AFRICA	0.25
KOREA	0.42
GERMANY	0.45
ITALY	0.46
RUSSIAN FEDERATION	0.52
FRANCE	0.97
INDONESIA	1.08
INDIA	2.89
MEXICO	2.91

Interpretation of Fig 4 (A & B):

India has the largest diaspora in the world. India is the first country which is having population of 17.50 million people living abroad or in other countries (Fig. A). Indians living abroad is the valuable assets for the Indian Economy. Inflows form remittances at 2.9% of GDP in year 2018-19 are comparatively large and represents stable source of income (Fig.B). The migrants of the India contributed in consumption, reducing poverty and education and health. Non-resident Indians also supports in domestic investments by mean of deposits in the financial system.

Fig 5.Export Performance could improve in some Sectors

Fig 5.TEXTILES, GARMENT AND FOOTWARE SHARE OF TOTAL MERCHANDISE EXPORT (in %)

	CHINA	INDONESIA	INDIA	VIETNA M	BANGLADES H
1995	30.63	15.63	29.71	28.82	79.68
1996	29.99	15.25	29.91	28.82	80.95
1997	30.31	11.13	30.09	28.82	83.10
1998		11.17	31.00	26.94	85.82

	28.61				
1999	27.41	15.74	30.33	29.69	87.22
2000	25.55	14.57	29.64	25.56	86.79
2001	24.62	15.13	27.29	26.70	89.08
2002	23.04	12.85	25.08	30.56	87.71
2003	21.36	12.28	22.72	31.92	88.64
2004	18.88	11.64	20.20	29.59	88.60
2005	17.86	10.90	18.35	26.98	87.01
2006	17.39	10.30	16.53	26.51	88.33
2007	16.41	9.36	14.62	27.12	86.42
2008	15.36	8.13	12.64	25.13	88.33
2009	16.57	8.80	12.46	26.72	90.12
2010	15.80	8.06	11.50	26.94	89.89
2011	15.74	7.44	10.61	25.44	90.72
2012	15.23	7.70	10.87	23.67	90.46
2013	15.64	8.44	11.59	24.35	91.76
2014		8.93	12.48	25.64	91.24

	15.50				
2015	15.22	10.52	14.62	26.47	93.25
2016	15.08	10.85	14.38	25.89	92.29
2017	14.27	9.98	13.18	23.56	92.17
2018	14.54	9.96	11.90	24.37	91.99

Interpretation of Fig 5:

Export performance of labor-intensive could grow faster. The export performances of textiles, leather and agricultural products have loosing share, thus limiting the positive impact of opening of trade or net job creation. India has stopped gaining market share since year 2013. Bangladesh now has large market share and after that Vietnam is coming forward to compete. Overall manufacturing export has fallen as a share of total exports. More dynamic manufacturing export would create jobs including for many unskilled worker having unemployment or they are under employed in the low paid organized sector. Increasing Manufacturing Export can create more and better jobs in India in the upcoming years.

INDIA FACING SEVERAL CHALLENGES

Fig 6. Wages are lower than other countries. (In US dollars)

COUNTRY	2018
PHILIPPINES	220
VIETNAM	227
INDIA	265
INDONESIA	296
MALAYSIA	413
THAILAND	413
CHINA	493

Interpretation of Fig 6:

The increase in Chinese workers income creates window for opportunity or we can say suitable time for Indians exports for at least for two reasons. First demand from China is increasing, including Indian Products. Second India is becoming more competitive in Labor- Intensive industries still India is behind the many other countries in the terms of wages. Clearly Speaking Because of scarce resources of capital and labor abundant and less productive workers, wages are relatively lower in India. They are regulatory wages and are expected to cover the essential current cost of accommodation, food and clothing.

Fig 7. Import Tariffs have been cut but remain high.

Fig 7.A. TARIFF RATES ACCORDING TO GOODS (In Percentage)

	CAPITAL GOODS	CONSUMER GOODS	INTERMEDIATE GOODS	RAW MATERIALS
2000	21.70	31.23	32.74	16.62
2001	22.37	38.52	33.62	19.59
2002	20.79	30.04	32.58	15.37
2003	19.65	28.00	29.46	14.71
2004	21.73	31.33	30.42	15.29
2005	9.60	17.56	17.95	11.73
2006	7.06	11.88	13.58	6.04
2007	8.36	16.60	17.69	7.24
2008	4.75	10.35	7.04	4.87
2009	5.44	9.46	12.04	1.78
2010	4.59	9.77	8.66	3.30
2011	5.35	9.55	11.33	4.76
2012	5.38	9.56	12.54	1.64
2013	5.33	9.56	12.57	1.69
2015	5.04	9.66	12.03	2.44
2016	4.57	9.59	8.05	3.53
2017	4.04	8.53	7.89	2.73
2018	4.11	8.23	7.10	2.03

Fig 7.B. APPLIED TARIFFS ARE RELATIVELY HIGH THAN OTHER COUNTRIES

COUNTRY	%
CANADA	1.54
UNITED STATE	1.66
EUROPIAN UNION	1.78
INDONESIA	2.09
JAPAN	2.47
VIETNAM	2.69
CHINA	3.88
SOUTH AFRICA	4.58
INDIA	5.79
BRAZIL	8.53

Interpretation of Fig 7 (A & B):

Import tariff rates have been cut sharply since the early 1990's. In Fig.7A.there are rates of tariff of various goods like capital goods, consumer goods, intermediate goods and raw materials. We can see the tariff rates are reduced too much compared to year 2000.(Fig.A) But still if we compare four types of goods Government of India Imposed more tariff to the consumer goods and intermediate goods.(Fig.A). India's tariff rates are relatively higher than other countries. High tariffs and frequent rate adjustments weigh on firms competitiveness.(Fig.B). Our higher tariff rates supports local industries and thus promote job creation in the manufacturing sector because they suffocate from competitive pressure. Therefore the domestic producers have to increase productivity. Also the complexity of India's tariff structure raises administrative and compliance cost. Lack of clarity on a tariff at product level creates some uncertainty.

Fig 8.A minimum use of Non-Tariff Barriers except Local Content and Anti-Dumping.

COUNTRY	SANITARY & PHYTO SANITARY MEASURES	TECHNICAL BARRIERS TO TRADE	BORDER CONTROL MEASURES	QUANTITATIVE RESTRICTIONS
THAILAN D	1.19%	1.61%	0.05%	0.46%
MALAYSI	0.97%	2.72%	0.03%	0.05%

A				
MEXICO	0.43%	3.24%	0.21%	1.22%
INDONESI A	0.96%	4.29%	0.85%	0.15%
INDIA	0.36%	5.51%	0.05%	0.36%
CHINA	0.24%	4.26%	0.97%	3.43%
SPAIN	1.29%	7.73%	0.12%	0.07%
But FRANCE	0.93%	8.83%	0.15%	0.11%
GERMANY	0.97%	9.10%	0.12%	0.11%
CHILE	1.13%	5.58%	0.01%	3.60%
UNITED KINGDOM	1.47%	8.61%	0.12%	0.16%
VIETNAM	2.00%	8.07%	0.23%	0.24%
JAPAN	1.56%	7.63%	1.27%	0.16%
COLOMBI A	1.46%	4.76%	0.38%	5.51%
UNITED STATE	1.88%	7.77%	2.46%	0.00%
AUSTRALI A	1.75%	8.01%	2.23%	0.24%
TURKEY	2.12%	7.99%	0.91%	2.40%
BRAZIL	1.53%	6.21%	1.46%	4.41%
CANADA	0.86%	8.57%	3.58%	0.59%
PHILIPPIN ES	1.37%	5.53%	2.27%	4.86%
NEW ZEALAND	1.43%	6.19%	0.30%	9.44%
ARGENTI	1.80%	6.83%	0.97%	7.97%

NA			
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Interpretation of Fig 8:

The percentage of products and share of imports covered by Non-Tariff measures are both relatively low in India. Sanitary and phyto-sanitary measures are mostly implemented in food sector often too overcome or reduce the impacts of market imperfections such as health risks. But we can see in the graph sanitary measures of India are comparatively very low. And also the quantitative restrictions, border control measures, technical barriers also low comparatively low than the China and other countries. Non-tariff measures may increase trade cost and fine more small companies with less access to legal and regulatory information. On the other hand, India depend on on local content requirements, wanting firms to use domestically produced goods and services. Anti-dumping measures are also used in particular on steel and chemical products.

Fig 9. Foreign Direct Investments are relatively Low (In % of GDP)

COUNTRY	AVERAGE	
	2000-2013	2014-2018
JAPAN	0.18	0.47
SOUTH AFRICA	1.79	0.83
ITALY	1.24	1.01
CHINA	3.64	1.66
FRANCE	2.35	1.67
INDONESIA	0.98	1.68
INDIA	1.57	1.77
UNITED STATE	1.76	2.13
GERMANY	2.69	2.13
CANADA	3.49	2.61
BRAZIL	3.07	3.9
UNITED KINGDOM	4.64	4.56

Interpretation of Fig 9:

India has liberalized its FDI policy in many sectors over the past two decades. While India as a share of GDP has remained relatively robust. If we see the

average of 2003 to 2013 India had 1.57% of GDP and from 2014 to 2018 it had only 1.77%. Therefore, compare to other countries in the graph India Improving its Foreign Direct Investments. The government aims at making India a more attractive FDI destination. FDI constraints in brand retail, digital media, contract manufacturing and coal sector were relaxed in August 2019. The governments indicated that further reforms in FDI include insurance sector, aviation and media sector.

VI.FINDINGS:

India is the topmost country in the population living abroad but in remittances India is on the second rank and Mexico is on First which is acquiring most of the percentage of GDP gaining from remittances.

Export performance could improve in some sectors like the labor intensive exports could grow faster because export performance of labor intensive sectors like Textiles, Leather, and Agricultural products losing share in the market since 2013.

Wages are lower than the other many competitors country.

Import tariff rates have been cut sharply since the mid-90's but still it is comparatively higher than other countries. High tariffs and frequent rate adjustments create burden on firms competitiveness because local industry cannot bear the competitive pressure.

The percentage of products and share of imports covered by non-tariff measures are both relatively low in India. Sanitary measures and border control measures are comparatively low than other countries.

Foreign direct investments are relatively low of India compared to other emerging economies (EME's). Restrictions on FDI remain higher than other countries.

VII.SUGGESTIONS:

India's migration can simplify the transfer of skills, knowledge and technology. I would like to suggest if 1/5th of Indian Students or workers living overseas return to home country. Indian investors acquiring skills from abroad may find application in India.

A focus on low technology segments like Textiles, Garments, Foot ware, Leather, and Agriculture industry would create jobs or employment for the many unskilled workers currently unemployed or under employed also the labor regulations are more inflexible for these industries. Introducing simpler and more flexible labor laws should be priority. Providing vocational training opportunities is also key to help workers to get ready for new and better paid skillful jobs.

In India not unemployment but wages are the real problems. It is still be easier to solve. Since country's labor laws have several issues that first need to be resolved and correct it.

In India, Low income households are most affected because tariffs on food items are high. Besides price reductions, lowering tariff rates would give households access to a large variety of goods also the domestic producers can improve productivity and quality of the products to face the competition from outside the country.

If India increase the percentage of sanitary and border control measures, it would create better impact on Food Industry and health Issues creating because of minimum use of sanitary and phyto sanitary measures (Non-Tariff barriers) and India already taking initiative in local content and imposing anti-dumping duties to protect some sectors.

More foreign investments could promote income growth in India. Liberalization and simplification in FDI policy could increase foreign investments in the country specially the banking, insurance, legal, accounting services and agriculture sector.

VIII.CONCLUSION:

In most countries, globalization increases incomes for many countries, but not all. The average income benefit of globalization is higher in emerging economies than in advanced and developed economies. In India high performing sectors tends to employ skilled workers, the ICT i.e., Information Communication and Technology is one of them but the labor intensive manufacturing industry has benefitted less from globalization.

India sees a globalization and trade as a positive element of development for employment and wages. Opening India further to trade and investments will entail a reallocation of resources and thus to reduce disparities across individuals and regions. Equipping people with the means to succeed in an open and dynamic world should be a priority

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